

The Kinetics and Mechanism of Cyclization of 1,5-Dianilino-2,4-Diphenyl Pent-1,4-Diene-3-One

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The various kinetic parameters of the cyclization reaction of 1,5-dianilino-2,4-diphenyl-pent-1,4-diene-3-one in presence of HCl which yields aniline hydrochloride and the corresponding N-phenyl- γ -pyridone derivative have been studied. A possible reaction mechanism that may explain the experimental results is discussed.

The reaction rate was found to be dependent of the dianilino compound and HCl concentration both to the first power and independent of the concentration of the products. The thermodynamic parameters of the activated complex were calculated. The high negative value of ΔS^\ddagger and the effect of substituents on the reaction rate are in accordance with the suggested pathway.

NO quantitative kinetic studies have been reported for the acid catalyzed cyclization of the dianilino compounds¹ or closely related compounds. Spectral studies² revealed that in the ultraviolet region the spectra of the dianilino compounds did not differ appreciably from their cyclization products. However the spectra of the dianilino compounds in the visible region exhibited an intense band at 410 nm which was not observed in the spectra of the cyclization products. The intensity of this band can therefore be used to trace the reaction rate.

Experimental

Reagents

All materials used were of the chemically pure grade. The dianilino compound and its derivatives were prepared as previously reported¹ and purified by several recrystallizations from benzene-ethanol mixture. Spectrally pure ethanol was prepared using the method introduced by Danner and Hildebrand³.

Rate measurements

The reaction rate was followed spectrophotometrically by measuring the absorbance at the visible region maximum at suitable time intervals. Beer's law was found to be valid in the concentration range used. A thermostated ZEISS PMQII manual spectrophotometer and one cm fused silica cells were used. The spectrophotometer was tested by comparing the absorption of a standard solution of alkaline K_2CrO_4 (0.04 g/l in 0.05N KOH) with that obtained by Haupt⁴. The two spectra were found to be in good agreement.

The kinetic runs were performed in 50% by volume ethanol-water mixture, by allowing both the compound solution and the acid solution, in the same

solvent composition, to reach thermal equilibrium in an ultrathermostat, the two solutions were then mixed and quickly transferred to the silica cell and placed in the cell compartment of the spectrophotometer through which thermostated water was kept circulating till almost about 75% completion of the reaction.

Results and Discussion

(1) Effect of the dianilino compound concentration

The order of reaction with respect to the dianilino compound was studied using the initial rate method. The concentration is expressed in terms of absorbance units. The rate can be expressed as

$$-\frac{d[B]}{dt} = k_0[B]^n[HCl]^m \quad \dots (1)$$

where B represents the dianilino compound. Since the HCl concentration was kept constant and in large excess with respect to [B], equation (1) can be expressed as,

$$-\frac{d[B]}{dt} = k'[B]^n \quad \dots (2)$$

where $k' = k_0[HCl]^m$ is the observed rate constant or

$$-\frac{d(A/\epsilon)}{dt} = k' \left(\frac{A}{\epsilon} \right)^n \quad \dots (3)$$

where A is the absorbance, ϵ the extinction coefficient and n the order of reaction. Equation (3) can be written as,

$$-\frac{dA}{dt} = \left(\frac{1}{\epsilon} \right)^{n-1} k' A^n \quad \dots (4)$$

thus,

$$\log \left(-\frac{dA}{dt} \right) = (n-1) \log \frac{1}{\epsilon} + \log k' + n \log A \dots (5)$$

The plot of $\log (-dA/dt)$ versus $\log A$ would give a straight line with a slope equal to the order of reac-

tion and an intercept equal to $(n-1) \log \frac{1}{\epsilon} + \log k'$.

Fig. 1. Determination of the order of reaction with respect to the dianilino compound.

The reaction was carried out in the presence of 0.0055 and 0.01N HCl at 35°. The values of dA/dt were taken as the slopes of the best tangents of the plots of absorption versus time plots ($\lambda = 410 \text{ nm}$) at different A values. The plots of $\log (-dA/dt)$ versus $\log A$ (Fig. 1) gave good straight lines, the slopes of which were 0.97 and 1.04 in case of 0.0055N and 0.01N HCl respectively. These values which might be safely approximated to unity left very little doubt that the rate of disappearance of the dianilino compound follows a first order kinetics with respect to the dianilino compound. This conclusion was confirmed by applying the first order kinetic equation. The reaction was carried out at 35°, the initial concentration of B varied from 0.81×10^{-5} to $6.58 \times 10^{-5} M/l$, while the concentration of HCl was kept constant and in large excess (0.0055N and 0.01N). The plots of $\log A$ versus time gave good straight lines. The constancy of the graphically calculated k' values, at constant HCl concentration (Table 1) confirms the results obtained by the initial rate method and supports the conclusion that the reaction is first order with respect to B, and equation (2) becomes

$$-\frac{d[B]}{dt} = k'[B] \quad \dots (6)$$

TABLE 1. DEPENDENCE OF k' VALUES ON THE CONCENTRATION OF THE DIANILINO COMPOUND

a) [HCl] = 0.0055N							
$10^5 \times [B]_{\text{initial}} M/l$	1.12	2.25	3.30	4.35	5.60	6.58	
$10^2 \times k' (\text{min}^{-1})$	5.87	5.90	5.90	6.00	6.26	5.97	
b) [HCl] = 0.01N							
$10^5 \times [B]_{\text{initial}} M/l$	0.81	1.22	1.73	2.18	2.62	3.49	4.35
$10^2 \times k' (\text{min}^{-1})$	11.05	11.05	10.94	10.82	10.94	11.20	10.82

(2) Effect of HCl concentration

The reaction was performed at 35° in solutions of the same initial concentration of B (3.7×10^{-5}) and different HCl concentrations ranging over 10 fold from 0.0033N to 0.033N which is relatively large enough to remain practically constant up to reaction completion. The chloride ion concentration was kept constant by adding the appropriate amount of KCl. Figure 2 illustrates the pseudo first order

Fig. 2. Dependence of reaction rate on HCl concentration in 50% (by volume) ethanol—water mixture at 35°.

plots of $\log A$ versus time. The graphically calculated k' values are given in Table 2. The plot of $\log k'$ (in equation (2)) versus $\log [HCl]$ (Fig. 3) gave a straight line. The slope of this line (m) amounted to 0.96 which is very close to unity leading to the conclusion that the reaction is first order with respect to HCl, and the rate law can be written as,

$$-\frac{d[B]}{dt} = k_0[B][HCl] \quad \dots (7)$$

TABLE 2. DEPENDENCE OF k' ON HCl CONCENTRATION.

[HCl]	0.0033	0.0055	0.0088	0.0110	0.0220	0.0330
k' in min^{-1}	0.0368	0.0610	0.0959	0.1180	0.2330	0.3450

(3) Effect of products

The cyclization reaction was carried out at 35° in 0.01N HCl, progressively increasing amounts of either the γ -pyridone or the anilinium salt were added to the reaction mixtures.

Fig. 3. Dependence of observed rate constant on HCl concentration at 35°.

The concentration of the added γ -pyridone ranged from 0 to $4.8 \times 10^{-2} M$ while the concentration of the anilinium ion ranged from 0 to $8 \times 10^{-3} M$. The graphically calculated k' values showed almost no variation indicating the independence of the rate on both products.

(4) Effect of temperature

The reaction kinetics was studied in the temperature range from 25°–40° in 50 vol. % ethanol-water containing 0.01M/l HCl and $3.09 \times 10^{-3} M/l$ of the dianilino compound. The pseudo first order plots at various temperatures are represented in Fig. 4. The Arrhenius equation is satisfactorily obeyed and the activation energy amounted to 11.7 K.cal/mole.

The entropy of activation was calculated from the rate constant k_0 by the use of the following equations⁵

$$\Delta F^\ddagger = RT \ln \left(\frac{RT}{h} \right) - \ln k_0 \quad \dots (8)$$

$$\Delta H^\ddagger = E - RT \quad \dots (9)$$

$$\Delta S^\ddagger = (\Delta H^\ddagger - \Delta F^\ddagger)/T \quad \dots (10)$$

The value of ΔS^\ddagger amounted to—26 cal/mole degree.

(5) Reaction mechanism

The mechanism of the cyclization reaction is discussed here in an attempt to build up a possible

Fig. 4. Pseudo first order plots in 50% (by volume) ethanol-water mixture at various temperatures. HCl = 0.01 N.

pathway for the reaction. From previously obtained results², it was concluded that, in acid solutions, a fast acid-base interaction between HCl and the dianilino compound exists. The rate of this interaction was supposed to be much faster than the rate of the cyclization reaction, since the red shift in the visible band of the dianilino compound occurred as soon as the acid was added. This shift which was attributed to the protonation of one of the nitrogen atoms is followed by the relatively slow decolourization giving the colourless products.

In the light of the above information and the experimental results obtained, two mechanisms can be suggested for the reaction: (i) a mechanism involving an intermediate carbonium ion (mechanism A) and (ii) a mechanism involving an internal transition complex (mechanism B).

Both mechanisms start with the protonation of (I) giving rise to (II) via a fast reversible acid-base interaction.

The intermediate (II) changes by a slow irreversible step into the unstable carbonium ion (III), which in its turn changes via a fast step to the product (IV). The positive charge on the protonated nitrogen in (II) facilitates the C–N fission. The nitrogen atom in (III) acts as a nucleophile, by virtue of its lone pair of electrons and attacks the positive carbon atom, thus leading to the fast formation of (IV).

In this mechanism, a transition complex is postulated through the nucleophilic attack of the non-protonated nitrogen on the carbon neighbouring to the protonated nitrogen. This attack is favoured by the formation of a formal positive charge on the carbon due to the neighbouring positive nitrogen. This mechanism can be considered as a special type of the concerted S_N^2 mechanism, save for the fact that it is intramolecular.

Mechanism A :

A support of the irreversibility of the second step (k_2), in both mechanisms can be found in the fact that the overall rate of the reaction was found to be unaffected by the addition of the products.

Mechanism B :

Mechanism (B) is more favourable than mechanism A since the carbonium ion in which the positive carbon is doubly bound to another carbon is not likely to occur. In support to this is the high negative value of ΔS^\ddagger of the reaction which is expected in the case of mechanism (B), which is an intramolecular S_N2 one⁶ involving a cyclic structure, while mechanism A, which is a special type of the S_N1 mechanism, requires a positive value of ΔS^\ddagger .

To derive a rate law for this reaction, the two

mechanisms can be represented as

in which the rate determining step is the second one. Thus,

$$\text{rate} = k_2[BH^+] \quad \dots (12)$$

Assuming a steady state concentration of BH^+ , one gets

$$[BH^+] = \frac{k_1[H^+][B]}{k_{-1} + k_2} \quad \dots (13)$$

Combining equations (12) and (13), one obtains

$$\text{rate} = \frac{k_1 k_2 [H^+][B]}{k_{-1} + k_2} \quad \dots (14)$$

If k_2 can be considered to be much smaller than k_{-1} , hence equation (14) becomes,

$$\text{rate} = \frac{k_2 k_1 [H^+][B]}{k_{-1}} \quad \dots (15)$$

$$= K_{eq} \cdot k_2 [H^+][B] \quad \dots (16)$$

$$= k_0 [H^+][B]. \quad \dots (17)$$

K_{eq} being equal to k_1/k_{-1} . Equation (17) is the same as equation (7) indicating that the assumptions involved are not far from being true.

(6) Effect of substituents on reaction rate

The effect of substituents in the para position of the phenyl groups attached to the nitrogen atoms was studied. The reaction was carried out for three disubstituted dianilino derivatives, *p*-, *p'*-dimethyl, *p*-, *p'*-dibromo, and *p*-, *p'*-dichloro, in the temperature range 25°–40° using 0.01*N* HCl in 50 vol.% ethanol-water mixture. Figure 5 shows a typical pseudo first order plots and Table 3 contains the graphically calculated k' values.

Fig. 5. Pseudo first order plots at 30°C. HCl = 0.01 *N*

TABLE 3. PSEUDO FIRST ORDER RATE CONSTANTS FOR DI-SUBSTITUTED DIANILINO DERIVATIVES (IN MIN⁻¹).

Compound t°C	Unsubs.	<i>p</i> -, <i>p</i> '- dichloro	<i>p</i> -, <i>p</i> '- dibromo	<i>p</i> -, <i>p</i> '- dimethyl
25	0.0552	0.0230	0.0196	0.1065
30	0.0748	0.0222	0.0276	0.1382
35	0.1094	0.0461	0.0415	0.1843
40	0.1405	0.0599	0.0541	0.2395

The presence of the methyl group causes an increase in *k'* values, by nearly two times, while the chloro and bromo substituents caused the value of *k'* to decrease to about 0.4 of that of the unsubstituted compound.

These results are in harmony with the proposed mechanism (B), since a methyl group in the para position will increase the electron density on the nitrogen; thus facilitating its protonation resulting an increase in the value of *K_{eq}*. The methyl group on the other phenyl, by the same reasoning, will make the attacking nitrogen a better nucleophile resulting in an increase in the value of *k₂*. Hence the overall effect will be a large increase in the observed rate constant.

On the other hand, the electron attracting chloro and bromo substituents might bring in the reverse effect in both *K_{eq}* and *k₂* and hence a large decrease in *k'* values.

If the alternative mechanism (A), is considered, the effect of substituents on *k'* values must be less than that in mechanism (B). In both mechanisms substituents will bring about the same change in the value of *K_{eq}*, however, their effect on the value of *k₂* will differ for the two mechanisms.

According to mechanism (A), electron attracting substituents will cause a decrease in *K_{eq}*, but it will cause an increase in the value of *k₂* due to the ease of the liberation of the aniline moiety with the formation of the carbonium ion. The changes of the observed rate constant will be dependent on the relative changes in *K_{eq}*, and *k₂*. The rate constant, could remain constant if the relative decrease in *K_{eq}* equals the relative increase in *k₂*, or it could increase if the relative decrease in *K_{eq}* is smaller than the relative increase in *k₂*, or it could decrease if the relative decrease in *K_{eq}* is greater than the relative increase in *k₂*. The first two probabilities can be excluded since they do not agree with the experimental results. The last probability, if actually occurring, would lead to a slight decrease (in the observed overall rate constant) which may be expected to be smaller than that obtained experimentally. Mechanism (A) postulates the three above mentioned probabilities while, mechanism (B) postulates only one, which is a decrease in both *K_{eq}* and *k₂*.

The effect of the methyl group, if discussed in a similar manner, will be the reverse of that of the chloro and bromo substituents.

The plots of log *k'* versus 1/T, gave good straight lines. The graphically calculated energies of activation, were found to increase in the manner *E_M* < *E_{unsubs.}* < *E_{Cl}* < *E_{Br}*. This trend can be visualized in the light of the Arrhenius equation and the values of the rate constants.

The other activation parameters, ΔH^\ddagger , ΔF^\ddagger and ΔS^\ddagger with the values of the activation energies of the different compounds are listed in Table 4. The values of ΔS^\ddagger are negative and almost constant at the different temperatures.

TABLE 4. THERMODYNAMIC DATA IN 50% (BY VOLUME) ETHANOL-WATER MIXTURES.

E, ΔF^\ddagger and ΔH^\ddagger in K.cal/mole; $-\Delta S^\ddagger$ in cal/mole. degree.

t°C	Compound	<i>p</i> -, <i>p</i> '- dimethyl	Unsub- stituted	<i>p</i> -, <i>p</i> '- dichloro	<i>p</i> -, <i>p</i> '- dibromo
	<i>E</i>	10.12	11.70	12.51	12.88
25	ΔF^\ddagger	18.47	18.87	19.38	19.47
	ΔH^\ddagger	9.52	11.10	11.91	12.28
	$-\Delta S^\ddagger$	30.03	26.07	25.07	24.13
30	ΔF^\ddagger	18.64	19.00	19.51	19.61
	ΔH^\ddagger	9.51	11.09	11.90	12.27
	$-\Delta S^\ddagger$	30.13	26.11	25.12	24.22
35	ΔF^\ddagger	18.78	19.10	19.63	19.71
	ΔH^\ddagger	9.50	11.08	11.89	12.26
	$-\Delta S^\ddagger$	30.12	26.03	25.13	24.18
40	ΔF^\ddagger	18.92	19.25	19.80	19.86
	ΔH^\ddagger	9.49	11.07	11.88	12.25
	$-\Delta S^\ddagger$	30.12	26.14	25.30	24.31

There is a small decrease in $-\Delta S^\ddagger$ on going from the methyl to the bromo derivatives. However, it could be concluded that the reaction mechanism was not changed by substitution.

Fig. 6. Hammett equation plots in 50% (by volume) ethanol-water mixture.

The Hammett equation, using the $\sigma\rho$ values obtained by McDaniel and Brown⁷ are shown in Fig. 6. The ρ values were found to amount to -1.56 , -1.58 , -1.65 and -1.74 at 40° , 35° , 30° , and 25° respectively. The negative sign of the ρ values showed that the reaction was hindered by the electron withdrawals and facilitated by the electron donors which is in accordance with the suggested mechanism. When the σ^+ values were considered, no straight lines were obtained. This is expected since neither of the substituents can be involved in a direct resonance interaction with the reaction centre.

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